

Preparation and Characterisation of Titanium Complexes with Ferrocenylcarboxylate Ligands

CHUNLIN MA*, HANDONG YIN, DAQI WANG, SHUHAO WANG and RUFEN ZHANG

Department of Chemistry, Liaocheng Teachers College, Liaocheng 252059, China

Manuscript received 5 April 1994, revised 31 October 1994, accepted 29 December 1994

In recent years, the chemistry of ferrocene and titanocene dichloride derivatives has been extensively studied due to their biological activity¹. The complexes $(C_5H_5)_2Ti(O_2CR)_2$ (R = alkyl and aryl) have been studied^{2,3}, but a few reports⁴ appeared for the complexes $(C_5H_5)Ti(O_2CR)_nCl_{3-n}$, especially with R group being ferrocenyl. We have prepared bis-ferrocenyl-carboxylmonocyclopentadienyltitanium(IV) chloride of the type, $C_5H_5TiCl(O_2CR)_2$ by the reaction of salt of the appropriate acid with monocyclopentadienyl-titanium(IV) trichloride.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (1-8) were synthesised according to the reaction,

where $n = 2, m = 1, z = 2, Y = FcCOO$ (1; 78%), $FcCH_2COO$ (2; 76%), $FcCOCH_2COO$ (3; 81%), $FcCOCH_2CH_2COO$ (4; 79%), $Fc(CH_2)_3COO$ (5; 82%), $FcCOC_7H_8COO$ (6; 85%); $n = 1, m = 2, z = 1, Y = 1,1'-Fc(COCH_2CH_2COO)_2$ (7; 83%) and $1,1'-Fc(CH_2CH_2CH_2COO)_2$ (8; 76%); Fc = ferrocenyl,

Although in the reaction the mole ratio of sodium salts of ferrocenecarboxylate and $(C_5H_5)TiCl_3$ was above 3 : 1, the elemental analysis data show that the complexes (1-8) are composed of $(C_5H_5)TiClY_z$, still another chloro-group being not replaced by ferrocenecarboxyl. It is possible that in complexes $C_5H_5TiClY_7$ the ferrocenecarboxyl groups have more steric hindrance². The results differ from the literature that the $(C_5H_5)TiCl_3$ reacted with sodium salts of alkylcar-

boxylate and $(C_5H_5)Ti(O_2CR)_3$ was obtained⁴

The complexes (1-8) are unstable and sensitive to light and air, also easily decompose upon heating (about 175°). They are soluble in organic solvents, such as benzene, acetone, methylene chloride, chloroform and tetrahydrofuran, but insoluble in water, petroleum ether, hexane and cyclohexane.

The ¹H nmr spectral data of complexes 1-8 are given in Table 1. The protons on the cyclopentadienyl group of titanocene shifted upfield (δ 6.31-6.50) as compared to that of the titanocene trichloride (δ 7.28)⁵. It is possible that the carboxylate groups are more electronegative than the chloro, leading to the decrease of circulating the deshielding effects of the cyclopentadienyl ring.

The ir spectra (Table 1) revealed characteristic stretching vibration of carbonyl of ferrocenylformyl in complexes 3, 4, 6 and 7 at 1665 cm^{-1} . In complexes 1-8, the $\nu_{C=O}$ carboxylato band was observed at $1700-1724\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but this band was not observed in the sodium salts of the corresponding carboxylic acid. It is shown that the effect of metal ions on ν_{O-C-O} is probably different. The carboxylate group in sodium salts exists in the form (A) but in the carboxylato derivatives of titanocene in the form (B),

(A)

(B)

It is to be noted that the difference of $\nu_{as}(O-C-O)$ and $\nu_s(O-C-O)$ is of importance since these frequencies can be used for determining the type of bonding

TABLE 1-¹H NMR (δ) AND IR(cm^{-1}) SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES 1-8*

Compd. no.	δ			ν_{max} (cm^{-1})					
	Ferrocenyl	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Ti}$	Other	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}^a$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	ν_{as}^b	ν_s	$\Delta\nu$	$\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$
1	4.28 (10H, s) 4.68 (4H, t) 4.79 (4H, t)	6.50 (5H, s)		1 708		1 630 (1 546)	1 360 (1 393)	270 (153)	651
2	4.09 (10H, s)	6.45 (5H, s)	FcCH_2 3.25 (4H, s)	1 720		1 644 (1 578)	1 357 (1 392)	287 (186)	643
3	4.18 (10H, s) 4.34 (4H, t) 4.50 (4H, t)	6.38 (5H, s)	FcCOCH_2 2.43 (4H, s)	1 724	1 664	1 617 (1 606)	1 320 (1 411)	297 (195)	650
4	4.20 (10H, s) 4.46 (4H, t) 4.81 (4H, t)	6.31 (5H, s)	$\text{FcCOCH}_2\text{CH}_2$ 2.59 (4H, t) 3.10 (4H, t)	1 718	1 666	1 632 (1 596)	1 374 (1 414)	258 (150)	657
5	4.01 (18H, s)	6.29 (5H, s)	$\text{Fc}(\text{CH}_2)_3$ 2.1-2.5 (12H, m)	1 722		1 643 (1 562)	1 350 (1 412)	293 (175)	648
6	4.27 (10H, s) 4.65 (4H, t) 4.82 (4H, t)	6.33 (5H, s)	FeCOC_7H_8 1.23-1.57 (4H, m) 2.9-3.3 (4H, m) 3.7 (2H, m) 4.43 (2H, m) 6.1-6.6 (4H, m)	1 719	1 665	1 630 (1 587)	1 370 (1 412)	260 (175)	674
7	4.50 (4H, t) 4.78 (4H, t)	6.38 (5H, s)	$\text{Fc}(\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2$ 2.66 (4H, t) 2.97 (4H, t)	1 700	1 664	1 635 (1 576)	1 341 (1 414)	260 (162)	674
8	4.05 (8H, s)	6.36 (5H, s)	$\text{Fc}[(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2$ 2.15-2.60 (12H, m)	1 723		1 629 (1 570)	1 317 (1 412)	268 (158)	633

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aCharacteristic frequency of carbonyl in carboxylate group.

^bAsymmetrical and symmetrical vibrations of sodium carboxylate groups, the differences being given in parentheses.

between metal and carboxyl⁶. This difference for complexes 1-8 is about 280 cm^{-1} , which is larger than the difference (165 cm^{-1}) for the appropriate sodium salts of ferrocenecarboxylates. Hence the carboxylate groups of complexes 1-8 are monodentate ligands^{2,7}. In addition, a new absorption band appeared at 650 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of vibrations of Ti-O bond formed⁷.

The electronic spectra of complexes 1-8 revealed bands at 221-241 and 257-263 nm of medium absorption, which are attributed to transition of cyclopenta-dienyl ring in ferrocenyl group and in titanocene^{8,9}. The charge transfer transition between the cyclopenta-dienyl ring and iron accounts for the

weak bands at 229-343 and 429-465 nm since the transition belongs to forbidden transitions. The weak band at 357-368 nm is attributed to charge transfer transition between cyclopentadienyl ring and titanium⁸.

The above results infer that the ferrocenecarboxylate ligands coordinate to titanium in the monodentate form.

Experimental

M.p. was determined using a Koff instrument. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Bruker FT-80A spectrometer relative to $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_4$, ir spectra (KBr) on a Nicolet FT-5DX spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a DU-7B spectrophotometer. C and H were

NOTE

determined by a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser.

Cyclopentadienyltitanium trichloride and ferrocenylcarboxylic acids were synthesised by reported methods¹⁰. Sodium ferrocenylcarboxylates were prepared from the corresponding ferrocenecarboxylic acids by reaction with sodium ethoxide in ethanol, followed by evaporation to dryness under vacuum.

Preparation of the complexes (1-8): All preparation were carried out under argon atmosphere. $(C_5H_5)_2TiCl_3$ (2 mmol) and an excess of anhydrous sodium ferrocenecarboxylate (1-6, 3.5 mmol; 7 and 8, 2.0 mmol) were added to dry benzene (50 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 12 h at 25°. The colour of the solution changed from the red-orange to yellow. The precipitated salt was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated to 5 ml under reduced pressure. Hexane (10 ml) was added to this solution and immediately an orange or yellow precipitate formed. The solid was crystallised from chloroform and hexane.

References

1. P. KOPF-MAIER and H. KOPF, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **87**, 1137; D. M. HOFFMAN, N. D. CHESTER and R. C. FAY, *Organometallics*, 1983, **2**, 48.
2. Y. MA and CH. MA, *Chem. Zvesti.*, 1989, **43**, 761.
3. D. MICHAEL, "Organometallic Compounds", New York, 1966, Vol. 1.
4. A. N. NESMEYANOV, B. V. LOKSHIN and O. V. NAGINA, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR. Ser. Khim.*, 1970, 90.
5. A. F. REID and P. C. WAILES, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 329.
6. K. CHANDRA, R. K. SHARMA, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 187.
7. Y. ZHOU, Z. WANG, X. WANG and Y. ZHU, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 783.
8. R. T. LUNDQUIST and M. CAIS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 1167.
9. H. H. JAFFE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 156.
10. R. D. GORSICH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4744; V. WEINMAYR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3009.

